

Regarding Table 7: Shared negative rankings of statements

Stmt. No.	Statement	Theme 1 Intrinsically Motivated	Theme 2 Altruistic Leaning	Theme 3 Sales vs. Fiduciary	Consensus Rank
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my boss.	-4	-4	-4	2
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and which ones to remove from my practice.	-2	-5	-4	18
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about individual PCA ¹ investor portfolio performance.	-3	-2	-5	15
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and single-topic solutions ² clients receive.	-5	-3	-1	29

¹ 'PCA' refers to Private Client Advisor, which describes financial advisors taking part in the study.

² 'Single topic solution' refers to planning services that are ancillary to core portfolio management.